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Abstract

In the 21st century, social media sites have developed rapidly and universally. This world has become a global village because of the widespread use of social media. There are millions of people using social media sites all over the world to meet a wide range of needs. There are many perks to using social media, including gaining knowledge of the world around you, alleviating boredom, and keeping in touch with friends. Using social media provides individuals with a vital source of social, moral, and emotional support, as well as a means of enhancing their cognitive abilities. According to the uses and gratification model, the current study aims to discover which social media sites in Pakistan satisfy university students' desire for social capital (Bridging and Bonding). Questionnaires were used in four public universities in Pakistan's twin cities of Islamabad and Rawalpindi to collect data on students' experiences in the classroom. Majority of people use WhatsApp to build social capital. Many respondents, on the other hand, say that Facebook helps them bridge their social capital.

Keywords: *Social media, Uses and Gratification, Social Capital, Bridging & Bonding Social Capital*

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Introduction

The amazingly rapid entrance of social media in the daily lives of individuals made it a significant platform for communication among them (Correa, Hinsley, & de Zuniga, 2010). Gallion (2010) explored that social media sites become hugely popular for social interaction with each other (friends & family) and professional connections got changed itself from offline to the online entity. Thus, social media empower its users to present themselves to the outside world, connect to either an existing social network or develop one of own and make new relations with maintaining the older ones (Ellison, Steinfield, & Lampe, 2007).

In the words of Boyd & Ellison (2007), social media sites are web-based services that allow individuals to: (1) build a public or semi-public profile within the system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system.

Social media sites play a vital role in building the network of a society. These networks are worth to understand its importance and advantages for individuals and also for the groups and sub-groups of society. An individual can develop social networks by starting relations with other people of the same society. The nature of these relations and relationships can be made both explicitly or implicitly; however, in either case, the relations are developed in order to benefit oneself or his/her society. This process of benefit may include the sharing of ideas, knowledge and information sharing along with other societal needs. However, some people also use these relations for certain emotional reasons.

Castells (2012) investigated that communication between individuals is been carried out through social media networks along with the organisation of collective action. While Van Dijk (2012) told that using these social networks could also harm or enhance the social relationship of individuals, and this is how they develop their social capital through these social networks.

Individuals make of online social media for many different reason like information, entertainment, social relationships by building new relationships & maintaining the older ones through different form of ties. They communicate in the form of posting pictures, video, sharing different stories, through the use of blog and tweeter, tag friends and leave comments on their posts which increase their social circle & eventually help them direct or indirectly. The ties individuals carry and the benefits they get through their social ties are referred to as social capital (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998).

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Objective(s) Of the Study

1. To investigate which social media site gratifies the need of social capital (Bridging and Bonding) of University students.

Hypothesis

Facebook is frequently used social site compared to Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp and Instagram for Bridging Social Capital.

WhatsApp is frequently used social site compared to Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram for Bridging Social Capital.

Facebook is frequently used social site compared to Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp and Instagram for Bonding Social Capital.

WhatsApp is frequently used social site compared to Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram for Bonding Social Capital.

Conceptual Context of Social Capital

Explaining the concept of social capital in a wider perspective is referred to the social resources or connections individuals accumulate through relationships with others in a social network. Bourdieu et al. (1992, p-119) defined social capital as *“the sum of the resources, actual or virtual, that accrue to an individual or a group by virtue of possessing a strong network of more or less established relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition”*. Woolcock (2010) found that social capital is the relations between individuals and groups in different social strata is a hierarchy where power, social status and wealth are accessed by different groups”.

Adler & Kwon (2002) reported that the concept of social capital is associated with different positive outcomes. Such social outcomes comprise good health condition (Public health), getting crimes to a lower rate and better financial markets. Putnam (2000) explored that the resources of social capital in the United States for the last couple of years is in the process of declining. And when there is a decline in social capital in a society, it has to meet the disorder in the social and civic activities, and there doesn't exist trust among the member of that society. On the other hand, an increased social capital that exists in a society increases the power of commitment of individuals of that society and connects them to perform collectively for a shared and common goal.

Social Capital is something that enables people to get connected with the resources of other members of the same network. These resources could be a piece of important information, the form of some good personal relationships or the abilities through which one can hold or tie a group together (Paxton, 1999). Granovetter (1973) found that when people go beyond their close circle and meet other people like people for employment etc. means that it always gives them access to some really useful information along with certain other forms of advantages. Researchers (Bargh & McKenna, 1999; Helliwell & Putnam, 2004) explored that ties of social capital and

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connections with friends and family are considered to be a sign of psychological well-being, like self-esteem and life satisfaction.

Bridging & Bonding Social Capital

In the context of social capital Putnam (2000) came up with the concept of bridging and bonding social capital. Bonding social capital associates to the close and tight connections exist among the individuals or groups who share similar attitude, characteristics along with potential available info and resources. This type of social capital offers individuals with social and emotional support which remains limited but highly connected and overlapped with each other. Coleman (1988) found that ties in the bonding social capital support unity among each other and are more rigid and resistant to new information. He added that the concept of bonding social capital is based on complex and dense relationship and it is, therefore, built very quickly because of homogenous characteristics and the member's association with each other over a long period. Woolcock (2010) argued that bonding relates to connections and interactions between homogenous community members such as neighbours and family members and is rooted in particularised forms of trust and reciprocity.

While bridging social capital is associated with a bridge or connections through which people from different demographics (race, ethnicity, class or religion) come closer and share similar socio-economic status (Putnam, 2001). Granovetter (1982) found that bridging social capital is related to loose connection and is referred to "weak tie." It is because of these weak ties people get the most useful information and perspectives without having emotional attachment or support. Granovetter (1973) further found weak ties to be more effective, helpful and far easier to get a job through compared to strong ties because it plays the bridge role to connect two different networks together.

Researchers have categorised these ties into two unlike types of social ties, i.e. the expressive social tie and the Instrumental social tie (Ibarra & Andrews, 1993). Granovetter (1973), in his work, reported that the former type of social tie does exist among very close people (Bonding). In this form of ties, they share friendship, social and emotional support from each other and are tied closely to each other. Umphress et al. (2003) argued that expressive ties got the strength for "conformity, persuasion and influence." While the later, Instrumental ties are considered to be the weaker ties (Bridging) which can be generated or formed casually at the workplace or anywhere (Ibarra & Andrews, 1993).

The use of social media for creating and maintaining social relationships got positive impacts on the structure of social capital directly through social networking tools or indirectly through the interest of communities (Zhang & Wu, 2013). Researchers have also found a positive connection between internet use and the development of both expressive and instrumental ties (Anderson & Rainie, 2010). Ellison et al. (2007) also reported that there is a positive connection/relationship between online social sites usage and increase expressive ties.

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Bridging, Bonding Social Capital on Geographical Basis

The concept of both bridging and bonding could easily understand on the basis of location. According to this context, bonding social capital is thus associated with the ties one have in his/her village while bridging could be the ties one have with the people or individuals of the nearby village. People in the same village got strong and dense relationships with a feeling of belongings among them. The created network is

exclusive, inward-looking and supportive in terms of access to information and resources.

On the other hand, bridging social capital which got ties in a different village(s), tend to have weaker bond/connection among the member because of rare contact. These ties are with different people with different skills and expertise living in a different village, and most importantly, they got a completely different social circle of friends. These ties help individuals with access to resources beyond an immediate connection through friends like the relation of a friend of a friend. This is how Putnam related bonding with “getting by” and bridging with “getting ahead.”

The geographical relevancy of bridging and bonding social capital somehow in traditional societies, however, in a modern society of a developed countries people from different origins live in close proximity, but they got less dense ties between them instead of stronger ones, and they hardly know each other.

Advantages of Bridging and Bonding Social Capital

Bonding social capital plays a vital role as a source of supporting people in a society who are suffering from socio-economic and health problems. It helps them “get by” and give them trust to facilitate collective action. Edin & Lein (1997) explored that, poor mothers, to meet their ends, obtain money from a network of family and friends but could not connect with people or social organisations which can help them, due to lack of bridging social capital. However, bonding social capital helped them to cobble together enough resources to survive.

On the other hand, Adler & Kwon (2002) found that bridging social capital enables individuals to connect to people far away, increase their abilities to gather information, provide them access to power in a network and make them able to identify new opportunities. Bridging social capital also help individuals with their accepting power of people from diverse societies, religions, values and beliefs along with tolerance in personality (Paxton 2002). These are the ties which bring people from different groups closer and enable them to exchange their skills, knowledge and innovative ideas they possess. Putnam (2000) told that this form of ties works as “social lubricant & leverage” which help people “get ahead”. Bridging social capital ties are inclusive, less dense and ever-changing (Widén et al. 2008). The weak bond in these ties is actually its power and strength. The same ties exist stronger in urban but weaker in rural communities, while the bonding ties are stronger in rural and weaker among the urban social networks (Woolcock 2010).

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Methodology

A detailed literature review helped the researcher to create relevant research questions for the current project (Rajasekar et al. 2013). This study tends to explore the “Role of social media sites in bridging and bonding social capital.”

This study used a series of methods and scales derived from previous research of Williams (2006) on an attempt to identify the role social sites like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp and Instagram for the gratification of social capital.

For the purposes of this research, the researcher interviewed 800 students from four universities in Pakistan's twin cities, namely the International Islamic University in Islamabad, the National University of Modern Languages in Islamabad, the Pir Mehr Ali Shah Arid Agriculture University in Rawalpindi, and the National University of Medical Sciences in Rawalpindi, to gather data.

Questionnaire was divided into two different parts: the 1st covers demographic details of students like sex, age, information about discipline, semester etc, while the 2nd part contains questions on Bridging and Bonding social capital through Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp and Instagram.

The researcher tried to know the perception of the students about the role of selected social sites for the gratification of bridging and bonding social capital. A descriptive analysis of 734 responses with a response rate of 91.75% has been done through SPSS 23.0.

Universe of the Study

The student community of the society has been taken as the universe for this study. As it can be said that students use social media more frequently compared to any other segment of society. There are plenty of reasons like using it for academic purpose, contacting teachers and fellow colleagues using it for organizing conferences and seminars etc. This is why they pay more attention to these site by spending much of their time.

This study focused on undergraduate students as the literature shows young students & adults have mainly demonstrated their interest in using new media like using social sites (Mohammed, 2011). The sample of students who were using social media sites was chosen from four public Universities of twin cities, Islamabad and Rawalpindi, i.e., International Islamic University, Islamabad, National University of Modern Languages, Islamabad. Pir Mehr Ali Shah Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi, National University of Medical Sciences Rawalpindi. The reason of choosing educational institutions was that they had respondents who were frequent users of social sites. Also, it was less time consuming to collect a large amount of data

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from the academic institutes rather in going to a non-academic segment where awareness about Internet and research is low.

The selected universities are highly reputed and well-known institutions in the twin cities and students from these Universities retain quality knowledge, experience, and backgrounds. Institutions, departments and faculties which remained part of the current project had been made on the experience of researcher with these faculties & convenient access to the respondents.

Characteristics of the Research Participants & Survey Sample

This research focussed on the experience of undergraduate students. Students of this group were selected because they are the most exposed group to internet use. "Pew Global Survey" explored that Pakistan has been ranked 8th among Asian top ten social media using countries and therefore 49% of the mobile phone users spend most of their time using social media sites performing so many activities⁴. This age group knows the dos and don'ts of internet use. They know what information or application they should use in order to gratify their different needs.

The sample size included 800 male and female undergraduate students from four different public universities of the twin cities of Pakistan, i.e. Islamabad and Rawalpindi.

The number of students to participate in the survey from across each university and faculty (present in each university) was decided using proportionate sampling technique keeping in mind the total number of students in each university and faculty, according to the record of each university and then used the purposive sampling technique to get to precise and accurate data.

Results

Table No 1.

Bonding Social Capital

There are several people in my contact list of, social site I trust to help solve my problems.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	58	7.9	7.9	7.9
Twitter	42	5.7	5.7	13.6

⁴<http://www.pewglobal.org/2011/12/20/global-digital-communication-texting-social-networking-popular-worldwide/>. Retrieved on 20th April 2012: Time 2:00 p.m.

YouTube	101	13.8	13.8	27.4
WhatsApp	512	69.8	69.8	97.1
Instagram	21	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows statistics of the 1st question regarding bonding social capital. Respondents were asked about the social site (contacts in that social site) which would help solving their problems. The table reveals that majority of the respondents 512 being 69.8% said that people in their contact list of WhatsApp would probably help them in solving their problems; 101 being 13.8% opted for YouTube; 58 being 7.9% said that their Facebook contact list would help them, 42 being 5.7% and 21 being 2.9% responded that Twitter and Instagram respectively are the social sites where there are people who would help them in solving their problems.

Table No 2.

There are some people in my contact list of, I can turn to for advice about making very important decisions.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	61	8.3	8.3	8.3
Twitter	58	7.9	7.9	16.2
YouTube	99	13.5	13.5	29.7
WhatsApp	495	67.4	67.4	97.1
Instagram	21	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The frequency table above indicates that majority of the respondents 495 being 67.4% seek advice from people in their WhatsApp contact list during big decision; 99 being 13.5% opted for YouTube; 61 being 8.3% said that their Facebook contact list help them in this regard, 58 being 7.9% and 21 being 2.9% responded that Twitter and Instagram respectively are the social sites where they seek advice from friends during an important decision.

TABLE 3

When I feel lonely, there are several people in my contact list, I can talk to.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	65	8.9	8.9	8.9
Twitter	37	5.0	5.0	13.9
YouTube	50	6.8	6.8	20.7
WhatsApp	546	74.4	74.4	95.1
Instagram	36	4.9	4.9	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The current table enquires about people in the contact list of a social site, which help respondents to talk to, during feeling lonely. The table discloses that majority of the respondents 546 being 74.4% talk to friends from the contact list of WhatsApp when they feel lonely, 65 being 8.9% opted for Facebook; 50 being 6.8% said that their YouTube contact list helps them in such a situation, 37 being 5% and 36 being 4.9% responded that Twitter and Instagram respectively are the social sites where they talk to people, in case of feeling lonely.

TABLE 4

If I needed an emergency loan of 5000 PKR, I know someone in my contact list of, I can turn to.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	35	4.8	4.8	4.8
Twitter	21	2.9	2.9	7.6
YouTube	64	8.7	8.7	16.3
WhatsApp	572	77.9	77.9	94.3
Instagram	42	5.7	5.7	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The data in the table above reveals that majority of the respondents 572 being 77.9% turn to people from their WhatsApp contact list in case of emergency loans; 64 being 8.7% opted for YouTube; 42 being 5.7% said that their Instagram contact list would help them while 35 being 4.8% and 21 being 2.9% responded that Facebook and

Twitter respectively are the social sites where they can find people from their contact list for an emergency loan of up to PKR 5000.

TABLE 5

The people I interact with in my contact list of, are good job references for me

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	71	9.7	9.7	9.7
Twitter	35	4.8	4.8	14.4
YouTube	114	15.5	15.5	30.0
WhatsApp	478	65.1	65.1	95.1

Instagram	36	4.9	4.9	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

In this table the researcher asked respondents about the social site (contacts) which help them as good job references? The table reveals that majority of the respondents 478 being 65.1% said that people in their WhatsApp contact list are the good job references for them; 114 being 15.5% opted for YouTube; 71 being 9.7% said that their Facebook contact list help them as good references, while 36 being 4.9% and 35 being 4.8% responded that Instagram and Twitter respectively are the social sites where they can find people from their contact list as good references.

TABLE 6

The people I interact with in my contact list of, would share their last Rupee with me

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	82	11.2	11.2	11.2
Twitter	42	5.7	5.7	16.9
YouTube	85	11.6	11.6	28.5
WhatsApp	504	68.7	68.7	97.1
Instagram	21	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The data of the current table reveals that majority of the respondents 504 being 68.7% agreed that people in their WhatsApp contact list would share their last rupee

with them; 85 being 11.6% opted YouTube for the same; 82 being 11.2% said that their Facebook contact list would do so, while 42 being 5.7% and 21 being 2.9% responded that Twitter and Instagram respectively are the social sites where they can find people from their contact list who would share their last Rupee with them.

TABLE 7

The people I interact with in my contact list of, would help me fight an injustice

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	93	12.7	12.7	12.7

Twitter	21	2.9	2.9	15.5
YouTube	106	14.4	14.4	30.0
WhatsApp	451	61.4	61.4	91.4
Instagram	63	8.6	8.6	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

In this table the researcher asked respondents about the strength of relationship a respondent have with his/her contact list in terms of help while fighting for justice. The table unveils that majority of the respondents 451 being 61.4% said that people in their WhatsApp contact list who would stand beside them in fighting against any injustice; 106 being 14.4% opted for YouTube; 93 being 12.7% said that their Facebook contact list would stand with them, while 63 being 8.6% and 21 being 2.9% responded that Instagram and Twitter respectively are the social sites where there are people in their contact list who would stand with them in case of any injustice.

Bridging Social Capital

TABLE 8

Interacting with people in my contact list of, makes me want to try new things.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	311	42.4	42.4	42.4
Twitter	24	3.3	3.3	45.6
YouTube	111	15.1	15.1	60.8
WhatsApp	156	21.3	21.3	82.0
Instagram	132	18.0	18.0	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The above table explores the views of respondents about which social media’s contact list help them try new things? The statistics reveals that majority of the respondents 311 being 42.4% said that interacting with people in their WhatsApp contact list make them try new things; 156 being 21.3% opted for WhatsApp; 132 being 18% said that their Instagram contact list make them try new things, while 111 being 15.1% and 24 being 3.3% responded YouTube and Twitter respectively are the social sites where interacting with people in their contact list make them try new things.

TABLE 9

Talking with people in my contact list of, makes me curious about other places in the world.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	385	52.5	52.5	52.5
Twitter	39	5.3	5.3	57.8
YouTube	142	19.3	19.3	77.1
WhatsApp	94	12.8	12.8	89.9
Instagram	74	10.1	10.1	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The current table unveils that majority of the respondents 385 being 52.5% said that talking to people on Facebook makes them curious about other place in the world; 142 being 19.3% picked for YouTube; 94 being 12.8% said that talking to people on WhatsApp makes them curious, while 74 being 10.1% and 39 being 5.3% replied Instagram and Twitter respectively are the social sites where interacting with people makes them curious about other place in the world.

TABLE 10

Interacting with people in my contact list of, makes me feel like part of a larger community

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	291	39.6	39.6	39.6
Twitter	50	6.8	6.8	46.5
YouTube	114	15.5	15.5	62.0

WhatsApp	183	24.9	24.9	86.9
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Instagram	96	13.1	13.1	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

This table investigates the views of respondents about being part of a larger community. The data reveals that majority of the respondents 291 being 39.6% feel to be part of a larger community when they interact with people on their Facebook contact list; 183 being 24.9% picked WhatsApp; 114 being 15.5% said that talking to people on YouTube gives them the feeling of larger community. However, 96 being 13.1% and 50 being 6.8% replied Instagram and Twitter respectively are the social sites where interacting with people makes them feel that they are part of a larger community.

TABLE 11

Interacting with people in my contact list of, reminds me that everyone in this world is connected.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	332	45.2	45.2	45.2
Twitter	49	6.7	6.7	51.9
YouTube	103	14.0	14.0	65.9
WhatsApp	162	22.1	22.1	88.0
Instagram	88	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The current table investigates the views of respondents about interacting with people on which social site’s contact list reminds them that everyone in this world is connected. The data shows that majority of the respondents 332 being 45.2% said that interacting with people on their Facebook contact list reminds them that everyone in this world is connected; 162 being 22.1% picked for WhatsApp; 103 being 14% said that talking to people on YouTube reminds them about the connected world, while 88 being 12% and 49 being 6.7% replied Instagram and Twitter respectively that interacting with people on these sites reminds them that everyone in this world is connected.

TABLE 12

Interacting with people in my contact list of, gives me new people to talk to

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	265	36.1	36.1	36.1
Twitter	78	10.6	10.6	46.7
YouTube	103	14.0	14.0	60.8
WhatsApp	128	17.4	17.4	78.2
Instagram	160	21.8	21.8	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The table (12) helps the researcher to investigate the views of respondents regarding interacting with people of which social site's contact list helps them to talk to new people.

The data shows that majority of the respondents 265 being 36.1% talk to new people when they interact with people on their Facebook contact; 160 being 21.8% picked Instagram; 128 being 17.4% went for WhatsApp, while 103 being 14% and 78 being 10.6% replied YouTube and Twitter respectively that interacting with people on these sites help them talk to new people.

TABLE 13

Spending time and talking to my contact list of, I come in contact with new people all the time

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	407	55.4	55.4	55.4
Twitter	51	6.9	6.9	62.4
YouTube	81	11.0	11.0	73.4
WhatsApp	85	11.6	11.6	85.0
Instagram	110	15.0	15.0	100.0
Total	734	100.0	100.0	

The table (13) helps to figure out the social site which helps respondents to get in contact with new people all the time. The table uncovers that majority of the

respondents 407 being 55.4% get in contact with new people all the time when they interact with people on their Facebook contact list while 110 being 15% told that Instagram help them meet new people. 85 being 11.6% went for WhatsApp, while 81 being 11% and 51 being 6.9% replied that interacting with people on YouTube and Twitter respectively help them get in contact with new people all the time.

Discussion & Conclusion

The tables here are an investigation of the social site(s) which is/are mainly used for the gratification of Bridging and Bonding social capital. The researcher asked respondents a series of questions about, which social site helps them to gratify the need of bridging and bonding social capital.

The data analysis made through SPSS revealed that WhatsApp remained the first social site which helps respondents with their bonding social capital. 69.8% people expressed that friends from WhatsApp would help them solve their problems, 67.4% agreed that they (Friends from WhatsApp) would help them in important decisions. 74.4% found friends from WhatsApp would helpful in the state of loneliness. 77.9% expressed that they have friends on WhatsApp who would help them with emergency loans. While 65.1% agreed with friends list from WhatsApp are quite helpful for job reference. 68.7% revealed that friends from WhatsApp social site are helpful to the extent that they would even share their last rupee with them. However, 61.4% responded that their friend would help them fight an injustice.

On the other hand, Facebook remained the first option of majority of the respondents for bridging social capital. For five out of six asked questions, majority of the respondents opted Facebook as their first social site, which helps in bridging social capital. 52.5% of the respondents expressed that friends from Facebook make them curious about other parts of the world while 39.6% agreed that friends from the same social site make them feel to be part of a larger community. 45.2% responded that friends from Facebook remind them that everyone in this world is connected, 36.1% expressed that friends from Facebook help them to talk to new people while 55.4% agreed that Facebook is the only social site, which helps them to connect with new people all the time.

Conclusion

The current project intended to investigate social media being a source of bridging and bonding social capital. Keeping University students in Pakistan as population, the researcher adopted quantitative research approach to conduct the study. Using a well-structured questionnaire, a survey is conducted in four public Universities of the twin cities of Pakistan i.e. Islamabad and Rawalpindi. A total of 734 students (Male and Female) with 91% response rate, participated in the survey.

The researcher hypothesized that Facebook is frequently used social site compared to Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp and Instagram for Bridging Social Capital or WhatsApp is

frequently used social site compared to Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram for Bridging Social Capital. Also Facebook is frequently used social site

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compared to Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp and Instagram for Bonding Social Capital or WhatsApp is frequently used social site compared to Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram for Bonding Social Capital.

The data revealed that students make social media use for bridging and bonding social capital. WhatsApp being the most popular among the student stood their 1st priority for gratifying bonding social capital. Individuals use WhatsApp regularly for their strong ties. On the other hand, Facebook has been found the most suitable for bridging social capital. People through Facebook make new friends & connections in the form of weak ties. The data thus concludes that the hypothesis which are Facebook is frequently used social site compared to Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp and Instagram for Bridging Social Capital and WhatsApp is frequently used social site compared to Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram for Bonding Social Capital are found accepted while the latter two were found rejected.

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